

Review of Rabindranath Tagore's *Santiniketan Essays Religion, Spirituality and Philosophy* by Medha Bhattacharyya. New York: Routledge, 2020. Paperback. ISBN 9780367442910. 170 Pages. Rs. 695

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Rabindranath Tagore cast a benign halo over modern Indian culture with his calm and optimistic philosophy. His outlook on life was based on the teachings of the Upanishads which encouraged contemplation and quiet introspection. The ultimate goal of this spiritual philosophy was the union of the human self with the Supreme Entity. A product of such thinking was Tagore's *Santiniketan* essays, a series of lectures delivered by him to a group of devoted residents of his spiritual abode, *Santiniketan* (abode of peace) which were later written down and published. They were 152 in number, published in two volumes in 1934-35. These were collectively named Santiniketan lectures possibly because they suggested ways to achieve everlasting inner peace. Among the fortunate listeners was Kshitimohan Sen, the maternal grandfather of the future Nobel laureate Amartya Sen. These were delivered between 1908 and 1916, when Tagore was at the peak of his creative powers. Significantly, Tagore won the Nobel Prize for the *Song Offerings*, a bouquet of spiritually reflective poems, in 1913.

In the volume under discussion, the researcher presents translations of fifty of these essays with a critical introduction and copious notes. The end notes explain a lot of typically Indian issues to the outside world e.g

the word karma and the story of Karna, the epic hero. Tagore's universalist ideas, the maturing of his thoughts and the socio-cultural context are reviewed here. Tagore's thoughts are connected to those of the noted savant of the then Bengal, Sri Ramakrishna Paramahansa and his noted disciple Swami Vivekananda. Interestingly, Tagore's relation with these two personalities was rather uneasy. This work is not a simple translation. It is an academic exercise in translation methodology and praxis, opening a new vista in Tagore studies. Quite a few pages are devoted to explain theory and technique of translation. It is interesting reading as the translator lucidly defines various technical terms such as Target Reader, Target Language and Source Language. She looks at translation from Bengali to English from the post-colonial angle. She tries to preserve the independent flair of the original Bengali. The author analyses the text from a linguistic angle. She places words used by Tagore in economic, legal, biological, spiritual and time calculation categories according to their nature. She also translated the relevant Sanskrit slokas.

In the preface of the work, Dr. Bhattacharyya describes her scholarly journey while pursuing her Ph.D project on this topic. She claims to have analysed Tagore's philosophical prose writings from a novel view point. For her, completing this assignment was a *sadhana* or meditation. Then she described the technicalities of the transliteration, especially the Romanization of Sanskrit, Pali and Bengali alphabets for non- Bengali and international readership. Part 1 of the book comprises of a long introduction. This includes several themes of Tagore's life, mostly connected to his prose essays. Tagore's personal life was rudely disturbed by sad events, including the untimely demises of his mother, wife and younger son. So he sought solace in spiritual meditation. Special emphasis is given to the period between 1908 and 1916. For better understanding of the Santiniketan essays his other literary efforts in this period are also discussed. Tagore's broad philosophy of life is delineated too. The significant difference between the Sanskrit concept of *Dharma* and the European term *Religion* is considered here. Dharma is a multi layered expression compared to religion. For Tagore Dharma

was the ideal way of leading life through performing assigned duties and maintaining perfect conduct. To follow Dharma one must develop a view of life or *jiban darsana*. Tagore stressed purity and simplicity over needless metaphysical wranglings. His view of life was not unnecessarily sombre. For him, emotions like joy and love were essential parts of life.

Dr. Bhattacharyya tries to arrange the essays according to a pattern in Part 2. The first essay of the collection is aptly titled *Arise! Awake* which should serve as an awakening call for the reader. This article sets the reader on his quest for inner peace. The second one, *Lack* makes the reader aware of the lack of God in his daily routine and its resultant harm. For Tagore Mother is the earthly representation of God. In the essay *Sin* Tagore cautions us of the ominous role of sin in obstructing our mental union with God. If we remain unconscious we may unwittingly commit sin. The next one *Sorrow* prepares us to embrace sorrow in order to attain truth. In the rest of the essays Tagore suggests ways of attaining Supreme Truth. According to him there is no need to renounce worldly life and become a monk to reach God. One can perform his everyday duties, take care of his family and still attain spiritual height. It is only necessary to keep alive the effort to attain Supreme Truth in one's heart even when involved in worldly affairs. One must not sit idle in the name of seeking God. Rather one must remain immersed in fruitful, constructive work throughout his life to attain *mukti* or ultimate freedom. As one discovers the inner truth he attains perfect harmony in life.

We can imagine an ethereal picture of Tagore preaching these lofty sermons like an Upanishadic savant in his green hermitage to a selected band of disciples during an absolutely quiet dawn. However the outside world was not so blissfully prosperous. Those were troubled years indeed. Tagore's home province of Bengal was cut into two by the British administrators in 1905. Tagore was an enthusiastic participant in the early phase of the Swadeshi movement which took off with unprecedented vigour to annul the partition of Bengal. Later he withdrew, disillusioned, from the movement. The product of his

disillusionment was the novel *Ghare Baire* or *Home and the World* (1916). Most disturbingly, communal tension raised its ugly head during the Swadeshi days. Ultimately, Bengal was reunited in 1911. But the capital of British India was shifted from Calcutta to Delhi. This, definitely, was a grievous blow for the Bengali gentry of which Tagore was a member. Outside Bengal, Mahatma Gandhi and his brand of mass politics became increasingly influential in Indian politics. In Asia, Japan was fast coming up as a developed, aggressive nation. There was political revolution in China too in 1911. In the international sphere, the major European powers were bracing themselves for a major conflict which finally broke out in 1914. This first World War fundamentally changed global politics and society. The Russian Bolshevik Revolution of 1917 was a part of the process. It is interesting to wonder what effect these turbulent events had on Tagore's mind as he delivered his philosophical sermons. In the last essay of the collection, significantly titled *Innermost Peace*, he observed that human hostility and warfare were causing disharmony in nature. But he was confident that God would ultimately ensure the "tune of peace" being played. Possibly he thought his lectures would make mankind noble enough to realize the folly of their actions.

Even now, the post-modern world remains turbulent owing to the new forces of global terror, post-colonial conflicts, cyber war, and unhealthy consumerism. In this context, Tagore's optimistic spirit as reflected in the Santiniketan lectures, offers some hope to the beleaguered citizens.

Dr. Bhattacharya deserves our praise for undertaking this translation project.